

Assessment Of Effective Communication Skills in Reducing Misdiagnosis and Enhancing Patient Safety Among Laboratory Staff at Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Specialist Hospital, Minna

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Abstract

The study assessed the roles of effective communication skills in reducing misdiagnosis and enhancing patient safety among laboratory staff. Fifty [50] Laboratory staff of Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Specialist Hospital, Minna were purposively selected from different departments, including Chemical Pathology, Microbiology, Haematology, Immunology and Gene x-pert Laboratory. The study rode on the information theory of the media and it was discovered that effective communication is very essential among laboratory staff in ensuring accurate diagnosis results [84%]. Inaccurate diagnosis outcomes can claim the life of a patient, causing the health care to lose its credibility in public. Also, training laboratory staff on effective communication skills helped to improve patient safety [81%] and promoted accurate diagnosis results [91%]. Data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire given to the Laboratory staff and collected data were coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences [SPSS] software. The study concluded that effective communication helps to improve patient safety and promote accurate diagnosis results among the laboratory staff. Besides, the study demographics cover individuals between the ages of 18 to >35 years covering five departmental laboratories and different marital statuses. The study results showed that effective communication among laboratory staff had a significant impact on diagnostic results and potential reduction in misdiagnosis. Also, the study results showed the effectiveness of communication training on staff development and improvements in client safety and treatment outcomes. However, the study recommended that laboratory staff should maintain effective communication skills and be trained on effective communication skills to promote proper diagnosis, reduce misdiagnosis, and ensure positive patient outcomes and safety.

Keywords: Effective communication skills, Hospital, Laboratory staff, Misdiagnosis, Patient safety

1.0 Introduction

Eke [5] defines communication as "a process through which individuals create and share meaning through symbolic interaction. Çelik and Alpanalso [2] also describe communication as "the relational process of creating and interpreting messages that elicit a response" [2]. Thus, through communication, individuals share one another's perspectives, practices, and understandings. The purpose of communication is broad; nonetheless, it could be limited to; getting and giving information,

which is by far the most popular purpose. It could be to persuade others to change their beliefs or behaviors or to get an action to be done, as possession of information may not be useful unless it is reflected in real life [1]. Effective communication is essential to sustain a thriving healthcare workforce and ensure patient health and safety. Besides, perfect managerial skills are required should the intention be to transfer the information accurately, clearly, and in a proper method. Nevertheless, communication does not only pass information and knowledge but also

brings a sense of relaxation and contentment to the sender and the receiver [2].

Research indicates that ineffective communication among healthcare professionals is one of the leading causes of medical errors and patient harm [7]. Recent reports from the Joint Commission indicate that communication failures continue to be implicated in a significant percentage of sentinel events, with over 70% linked to these issues [15]. This highlights the ongoing need for improved communication strategies in healthcare settings. Besides, the study by Dayom et al. [3], highlighted that communication failures between nurses and physicians continue to be a significant factor in patient care errors. The report emphasized the need for improved interdisciplinary communication and collaboration to enhance patient safety and reduce the incidence of errors in healthcare settings [3]. Wondmieneh et al. [18] asserted that intimidation and communication barriers continue to be significant factors contributing to medication errors [16]. The study revealed that a substantial number of healthcare professionals still report feeling pressured to administer medications despite safety concerns, indicating a persistent issue with communication dynamics in clinical settings [16]. Furthermore, Manias et al., [11] in their study discuss the impact of communication failures on patient safety and outcomes in acute care environments, highlighting the need for improved communication strategies among healthcare teams [10].

Consequently, the recent study by Sexton et al. [15] examined communication in healthcare teams and found that ineffective communication among medical staff, particularly in intensive care units, significantly contributes to increased patient safety risks and longer hospital stays [13]. This was corroborated by Kirkpatrick et al. [9] who highlighted the correlation between communication breakdowns among healthcare providers and higher rates of patient adverse events in critical care settings [9]. Researchers analyzed 421 operating room communications, finding failures in 30% of exchanges, which jeopardized patient safety by increasing cognitive load and tension [6]. According to Kim et al. [8], Lingard and colleagues identified four categories of communication problems: communications that were too late to be effective, failure to communicate with all relevant team members, incomplete and inaccurate content, and communications that did not achieve their

purpose, leaving issues unresolved until urgency arose [8].

Similarly, teamwork and effective communication are crucial for safe patient care, a gap exists in the educational curricula in most healthcare professions; the focus is primarily on individual technical skills, neglecting teamwork and communication skills [6]. However, Healthcare providers must be conscious of patient safety incidents [PSIs] risks and take steps to prevent them as much as possible [12]. Most healthcare organizations have, therefore, initiated and prioritised patient safety strategies to prevent PSIs from occurring. This includes implementing evidence-based practices, improving communication among healthcare team members, and investing in quality improvement efforts [12]. In this vein, this paper aims to explore the roles of effective communication skills in reducing misdiagnosis and enhancing patient safety among laboratory staff at Ibrahim Babangida Specialist Hospital, Minna. The following objectives of the study are to assess the impact of effective communication skills among laboratory staff on the accuracy of diagnostic results and reduction in misdiagnosis and to examine the relationship between communication training for laboratory staff and improvements in patients' safety outcomes.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The research was carried out at the Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Specialist Hospital, Minna. The hospital lies between latitude 19° 36'54.86" N and longitude 6° 32'52.94" E [Google Maps]. Staff from six [6] departmental laboratories comprising Chemical Pathology, Microbiology, Haematology, Immunology and Gene x-pert were chosen for the study.

2.2 Study Design

The study is a quantitative design that uses a survey or self-reported questionnaire. The study design entails establishing the research question, choosing a suitable sampling technique, creating a questionnaire with simple, straightforward questions, sending it out to the target audience, gathering and evaluating the data, and interpreting the findings [10]. This approach makes it possible to gather and analyze data efficiently, especially

when researching the beliefs, attitudes, or actions of a sizable population [10].

2.3 Study Population

The study population comprises fifty [50] laboratory staff of the Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida Specialist Hospital, Minna.

2.4 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample comprises staff aged ≥ 18 years cutting across five [5] departments of Chemical Pathology, Microbiology, Haematology, Immunology and Gene x-pert. The sampling technique employed by the study is convenience sampling as participants are selected based on their availability and ease of access [14].

2.5 Instruments for Data Collection

The study used an open-ended self-reported questionnaire [5-Likert scale questionnaire] for data collection from respondents.

2.6 Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The study validity is premised on the questionnaire covering all aspects of the research hypothesis and theoretical framework and assesses how well respondents' responses correlate with external measures and outcomes. This is attained through a clear definition of the study objectives, the use of expert reviews to refine study questions, and the identification and testing of ambiguities. However, instrument reliability is determined by measuring the consistency of the administered, inter-rater reliability to interpret respondents' responses, and internal consistency, which examines whether the question measuring the same concept produced similar responses. This is attained by using unambiguous sentences, providing guidelines on response interpretation, and minimizing subjective bias through evaluator training.

2.7 Method for Data Collection

Data were collected using an open-ended self-reported questionnaire. The questionnaire has a 5-point Likert rating.

2.8 Data Analysis

The data collected were coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences [SPSS]

software. Results were presented in frequency, percentage counts, Mean and Standard Deviation.

3.0 Results

3.1 Demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Item 1 in the table shows the age distribution of the respondents. It was discovered that 8 [16%] of the respondents are between the age of 18-25, 14 [28%] of the respondents are between the age of 26-30, 18 [36%] of the respondents are between the age of 31-35, while 10 [20%] are 36 and above of age, however, the listed age brackets were given an equal opportunity but majority of the respondents are between the age of 31-35. Item 2 shows the department of the respondents and 10 respondents representing [20%] were selected from each department. There is equality in the selection of respondents in the five laboratory departments which include; the Chemical Pathology department, Microbiology, Haematology, Immunology and Gene x-pert Laboratory department. Also, item 3 shows the marital status of the respondents and it was discovered that 11 [22%] of the respondents are single, 37 [74%] of the respondents are married, 2 [4%] of the respondents are separated, while no respondent filled the divorce section. This shows that the majority of the respondents are married.

3.2 Response on the Impact of effective communication skills among laboratory staff on the accuracy of diagnostic results and reduction in misdiagnosis

The Table 2 presents data on the impact of effective communication skills among laboratory staff on the accuracy of diagnostic results and reduction in misdiagnosis. The analysis results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that effective communication is very important among laboratory staff in ensuring accurate diagnosis results [Mean=3.35, Standard Deviation=1.81]. Also, they strongly agreed regarding their agreement that effective communication skills contribute to a reduction in misdiagnosis [Mean=3.57, Standard Deviation=1.71]. More so, respondents strongly agreed that effective communication skills build a good relationship between laboratory staff and the patients [Mean=3.90, Standard Deviation=1.73]. However, the majority of the respondents strongly agreed that effective communication skills help to reduce patients' mortality [Mean=3.45, Standard Deviation=1.23]. With these, it can be concluded

that effective communication skills play a crucial role among laboratory staff in the accuracy of diagnostic results and reduction in misdiagnosis.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Respondents' Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18-25	8	16%
26-30	14	28%
31-35	18	36%
36 and above	10	20%
Total	50	100%
Department		
Chemical Pathology	10	20%
Microbiology	10	20%
Haematology	10	20%
Immunology	10	20%
Gene x-pert Laboratory	10	20%
Total	50	100%
Marital Status		
Single	11	22%
Married	37	74%
Separated	2	4%
Divorce	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Table 2: Response on the Impact of effective communication skills among laboratory staff on the accuracy of diagnostic results and reduction in misdiagnosis

Items	Level of Choice*[%]					Mean	Std. Deviation	Overall %
	1	2	3	4	5			
Effective communication is very important among laboratory staff in ensuring accurate diagnosis result	3	7	8	31	51	3.35	1.81	84
Effective communication skills contribute to a reduction in misdiagnosis	5	6	9	22	58	3.57	1.71	84
Effective communication skills build a good relationship between laboratory staff and patients	8	5	14	28	45	3.90	1.73	98
Effective communication skills help to reduce patients' mortality	4	3	7	22	64	3.45	1.23	86
Total						3.57	1.62	88

*Scale: 1=Strongly Disagree [1-20%], 2=Disagree [21-40%] 3=Neutral [41-60%], 3=Agree [61-80%], 5=Strongly Agree [81-100%].

3.3 Respondents' response on the Relationship between communication training for laboratory staff and improvements in patients' safety outcomes

The table presents data on the relationship between communication training for laboratory staff and improvements in patients' safety outcomes. The analysis results indicate that respondents strongly agreed that hospitals should always engage the laboratory staff in communication training [Mean=3.40, Standard Deviation=1.44]. Also, they strongly agreed regarding their agreement on training laboratory staff on effective

communication skills helps to improve patient safety [Mean=3.24, Standard Deviation=1.92]. More so, respondents strongly agreed that communication training for laboratory staff promotes accurate diagnosis results [Mean=3.63, Standard Deviation=1.81]. However, most respondents strongly agreed that patients' safety becomes a priority of the laboratory staff once there is effective communication [Mean=3.51, Standard Deviation=1.25]. With these, it can be concluded that training Laboratory staff on effective communication skills helps the staff to improve patients' safety.

Table 3: Respondents' response on the Relationship between communication training for laboratory staff and improvements in patients' safety outcomes

Items	Level of Choice*[%]					Mean	Std. Deviation	Overall %
	1	2	3	4	5			
Hospitals should always engage the laboratory staff in communication training	8	7	11	33	41	3.40	1.44	85
Training of laboratory staff on effective communication skills helps to improve patient safety	2	4	12	37	45	3.24	1.92	81
Communication training for laboratory staff promotes accurate diagnosis result	6	8	27	35	24	3.63	1.81	91
Patients' safety becomes a priority of the laboratory staff once there is an effective communication	11	2	23	19	45	3.51	1.25	88
Total						3.45	1.61	86

*Scale: 1=Strongly Disagree [1-20%], 2=Disagree [21-40%] 3=Neutral [41-60%], 3=Agree [61-80%], 5=Strongly Agree [81-100%].

4.0 Discussion

This study aims to unveil the roles of effective communication skills in reducing misdiagnosis and enhancing patient safety among laboratory staff. Fifty [50] respondents were samples from Ibrahim Babangida Specialist Hospital, Minna, Niger State and they were selected from Chemical Pathology, Microbiology, Haematology, Immunology and Gene x-pert Laboratory departments. According to the respondents' demographics, the plurality [36%]

is between the ages of 31 and 35, with 28% being between the ages of 26 and 30. This suggests that the majority of the laboratory staff is made up of people who have probably accumulated a significant amount of expertise in their respective fields. A sizable portion of responders were between the ages of 31 and 35, which indicates job stability, which might enhance professional relationships and communication abilities. Younger employees may be in training or entry-level roles, which could explain their lower representation, as

only 16% of respondents are between the ages of 18 and 25. The significance of expertise in laboratory settings, where clear communication is essential for precise diagnosis and patient safety, is highlighted by this age distribution. Also, differences in age demographics may be due to the age requirements for employment specified by the civil service or public service rule, which indicate that employment in the service is for individuals ≥ 18 years [11].

With 10 people [20%] from Chemical Pathology, Microbiology, Hematology, Immunology, and Gene X-pert Laboratories, the data shows equal representation from each laboratory department. This well-rounded selection highlights the collaborative nature of laboratory work and enables a thorough grasp of viewpoints from many laboratory specialties. The equitable distribution reflects the combined experiences of laboratory personnel in various disciplines and implies a dedication to promoting interdisciplinary collaboration, which is essential for guaranteeing reliable diagnostic results. The vast majority of respondents [74%] are married, compared to 22% who are single and 4% who are separated. Interestingly, none of the respondents said they were divorced. Given that marriage is frequently regarded as a virtue in many cultures, the prevalence of married people may be a reflection of societal influences, as it is higher among professionals. Married people may also look for steady work in healthcare environments, especially in positions requiring dedication and dependability [4]. Given that interpersonal skills are frequently improved by established personal relationships, the results imply that married staff members may communicate more effectively. This majority might represent a staff that prioritizes teamwork, which would enhance patient outcomes.

The demographic data provides a framework for understanding the association between good communication abilities and patient safety results. The age distribution shows experienced personnel tend to prioritize communication in their employment. The equal representation of departments emphasizes how important it is for diverse laboratory specialties to work together and communicate effectively [14]. Furthermore, the large proportion of married respondents points to a workforce that is more concerned about how their work affects patient safety since they may connect their work obligations to personal lives [4]. This link highlights how crucial it is to promote a culture

of communication in healthcare environments, motivating employees to put patient safety first.

It was discovered from the study that communication is very essential in every profession and not just to communicate, but to communicate effectively. Since laboratory staff deal with patient diagnosis, it was observed that effective communication is very important among laboratory staff in ensuring accurate diagnosis results [84%]. Inaccurate diagnosis outcomes can claim the life of the patient, making the health care lose its credibility in public. Laboratory staff of Ibrahim Babangida Specialist Hospital also noted that effective communication skills contribute to a reduction in misdiagnosis. This aligns with Sharkiya's [16] findings, which emphasized the importance of communication skills in enhancing service effectiveness and improving patient care outcomes in healthcare settings [14]. Therefore, the findings of this study highlight that effective communication among health information management practitioners is vital for minimizing errors and improving overall healthcare delivery

More so, where there is the presence of effective communication skills among the health practitioners, it helps to build a good relationship between laboratory staff and the patients [98%], hence, it reduces patients' mortality. This corroborates with Poku et al. [13] whose study discovered that most healthcare organizations have initiated and prioritised patient safety strategies to prevent PSIs from occurring [12]. This includes implementing evidence-based practices, improving communication among healthcare team members, and investing in quality improvement efforts. Similarly, the habit of communicating effectively can also be taught to improve the staff proficiency and project the hospital standard. It was discovered that to ensure Ibrahim Babangida Specialist Hospital actualize effective communication skills among its staff, the management should always engage the laboratory staff in communication training [85%]. Because training laboratory staff on effective communication skills helps to improve patient safety [81%] and promote accurate diagnosis results [91%]. Consequently, the effective communication skills of the laboratory staff in various departments, and patients' safety becomes the priority of the staff at Ibrahim Babangida Specialist Hospital. This correlates with Hopkins et al. [6] whose study discovered that there are associations between higher nurse-physician communication/collaboration and positive patient

outcomes: lower mortality, higher satisfaction, and lower readmission rates [6].

5.0 Conclusion

The investigation revealed a broad age distribution among respondents, with the majority in the 31-35 age range. Respondents were evenly selected from five laboratory departments, and most were married, indicating a primarily married demographic. Effective communication skills were deemed essential for accurate diagnostic outcomes and reducing misdiagnosis, while also facilitating strong relationships between staff and patients. Respondents overwhelmingly supported ongoing communication training for laboratory personnel, recognizing its importance in enhancing patient safety and fostering accurate diagnoses. Effective communication skills are imperative for the laboratory staff at Ibrahim Babangida Specialist Hospital, Minna, to ensure error-free diagnoses and effectively convey results to patients. Training in effective communication should be foundational in healthcare settings, including Ibrahim Babangida Specialist Hospital, emphasizing the significance of laboratory equipment and clear communication of results. These findings demonstrate that improving communication is crucial for enhancing diagnostic accuracy and patient outcomes.

6.0 Recommendations

The study, recommends that laboratory staff should maintain effective communication skills to enhance diagnosis and improve patients' safety.

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